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Table of Content

Vol. 7, Issue 1 – 2022

S. No.	Articles	Page No.
1.	Delineation of Ground Water Potential Zones using Remote Sensing, GIS and Geophysical Technique in Harahua Block, District Varansi, Uttar Pradesh Dr. Ritu Jain	01-22
2.	Measuring Subjective Happiness and Life Satisfaction among Jamaicans during the COVID-19 Pandemic Paul Andrew Bourne, Priscian Vassell, Kimberly Brown, Kimberly Cooke, Chadine Pryce, James Fallah, Calvin Campbell, Clifton Foster, Caroline McLean, Dian Russell-Parkes, Monique White, Tabitha Muchee	23-49
3.	Philosophical Principles of the Concept of the Good Life in Indian Ethics Dr. Ajay Krishna Tiwari	50-56
4.	Adjustment among Joint and Nuclear Family Students-A Comparative Study Shilpi Gupta, Dr. Suraksha Bansal	57-64
5.	A Thoughtful Analytical Study on the Criminalization of Politics and Corruption in the Administration Dr. Ajay Krishan Tiwari	65-69
6.	Citizenship and the Governance Imbroglia in Nigeria Falegan, Temitope1 , Akele, Oluwabanji Adeoluwa	70-83
7.	Environmental Decision Making-Access to Information and Public Participation Faizan Khan	84-90
8.	National Education Policy 2020-Challenges and Implementation in Higher Education Dr. AlkaAsthana, Namita Rajpal	91-97